

ANALYSIS OF HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT COMMITMENT TOWARDS THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DISASTER MANAGEMENT AT BHAYANGKARA HOSPITAL BANDA ACEH

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Abstract

Disasters are events and series of events that can threaten and disrupt people's lives and livelihoods. In 2004, the earthquake and tsunami in Aceh destroyed hospitals and other health facilities and in 2020 the Covid 19 outbreak occurred which was a national epidemic. The existence of a strong management commitment is very necessary for hospitals to be able to increase hospital readiness in facing disasters. The aim of this research is to analyze management commitment in implementing disaster preparedness at Bhayangkara Hospital. This research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach that collects data using observation, document review and in-depth semi-structured interviews. There were 5 informants, namely 1 key informant, 1 main informant and 3 additional informants. Where the resulting data is then analyzed using an interactive model. The research results show that there is management commitment regarding the organizational structure of disaster management, infrastructure, procedures, resources, financing and training. However, the performance of disaster management has not been optimal even though the hospital uses the concept of activation and deactivation of the organizational structure. Disaster management facilities and infrastructure require additions. And most employees have received training related to disaster management at Bhayangkara Hospital. All informants have a commitment and analysis of the implementation of disaster management using the Hospital Disaster Plan Guidelines as a measuring tool or disaster indicator.

Keywords: *Commitment, Hospital Management,*

1. INTRODUCTION

Although unpredictable, disasters must be managed. Disaster management planning is needed to reduce the impact of natural disasters, one of the methods used is disaster mitigation. Disaster mitigation is a series of steps taken to reduce the risk and vulnerability to disasters. According to Law No. 24 of 2007, disaster management is a dynamic, ongoing, and integrated process to improve the quality of steps related to disaster observation and analysis as well as prevention, mitigation, preparedness, early warning, emergency response, rehabilitation and reconstruction of disasters. According to Warfield, disaster management aims to reduce, or prevent, losses due to disasters, ensure the implementation of immediate and adequate assistance to disaster victims, achieve rapid and effective recovery. Disasters are events and series of events that can threaten and disrupt the lives and livelihoods of people

due to, either natural factors or non-natural factors and human factors, resulting in the emergence of human casualties, the environment, and property and will have an impact on psychology. (Pahleviannur.MR, 2019)

Hospitals as service providers must carry out their duties in accordance with the Standard Operating Procedure in organizing health services. Disaster management in hospitals is carried out with the aim of preventing more victims, protecting all patients and health workers. Disasters can occur anywhere, including in hospitals. Disasters in hospitals can occur due to natural disasters but can also be caused by disasters due to work accidents, due to the failure of the hospital's occupational safety and health program, poor physical planning of buildings, and the absence of maintenance and supervision of sources of danger. (Murni, et. al.2014)

Disasters in Hospitals are disasters that occur inside and/or outside the Hospital that can affect service functions. Implementation of Disaster Management is a series of efforts that include determining disaster risk policies, prevention activities, emergency response, and rehabilitation. (Ministry of Defense Regulation, 2014) Various types of disasters that may occur in hospitals, both internal and external disasters (fire, earthquake, flood, tsunami, etc.), the risk hazards that occur in the hospital have been successfully overcome with proper planning (hospital disaster plan)

Bhayangkara Hospital Banda Aceh is a police-owned hospital located in Meuraxa District, Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam Province. The Banda Aceh City Government has determined the Operational Permit and Class Type D Determination of Bhayangkara Hospital Class IV Banda Aceh on February 13, 2017 through the Decree of the Head of the Capital Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Office of Banda Aceh City Number: 87 concerning Permanent Operational Permit and Class Type D Determination. Based on the Decree of the Head of KARS Number: KARSSERT / 669 / I / 2018 on January 17, 2018, Bhayangkara Hospital Class IV Banda Aceh was declared to have passed the First Level Hospital Accreditation.

Bhayangkara Hospital is able to provide health services to the community with the facilities it has. After the tsunami, this hospital continued to develop disaster service programs by preparing infrastructure and resources as well as a budget for disasters. During the Covid 19 period, this hospital also served Covid 19 patients by preparing special isolation rooms, infrastructure, and PPE according to standards. In this case, it can be used as an illustration that the hospital owner has a commitment to provide emergency services at the Bhayangkara Hospital. The existence of the Bhayangkara Hospital is one of the trusted health service places and is the main choice for the surrounding community, especially the Polri community. In carrying out disaster services at the Bhayangkara Hospital, it is guided by Permenken No. 66 of 2016 concerning Occupational Health and Safety in Hospitals, Permenkes No. 11 of 2017 concerning patient safety and technical guidelines for the Decree of the Head of the Bhayangkara Hospital No. Kep / 16 / I / Kep.4.2 / 2023 / RS.BHY concerning the establishment of a hospital Occupational Health and Safety Committee.

In the decree of the head of the hospital regarding the hospital's occupational health and safety committee, the organizational structure is stated with the following composition: committee chairman, secretary and three coordinators consisting of the K3RS coordinator for occupational health and safety, the K3RS coordinator for environmental sanitation and the coordinator for fire and disaster preparedness. In the K3RS committee structure, there is a fire

and disaster preparedness coordinator, there is a training program and simulation of the use of fire extinguishers, patient evacuation simulation. Therefore, the researcher wants to see how the strategy, policy, commitment of hospital management in implementing disaster preparedness. Based on the programs and activities that have been carried out by the hospital, there are still many things that need to be done to support the implementation of disaster management at the Bhayangkara Hospital so that it is in accordance with the standards of disaster regulations in hospitals.

1.1 Research Objectives:

1. Describe the disaster management strategy at Bhayangkara Hospital Banda Aceh.
2. Describe the commitment to implementing disaster management at Bhayangkara Hospital Banda Aceh
3. Analyze the management commitment to implementing disaster management at Bhayangkara Hospital Banda Aceh.

1.2 Research Contribution:

For Hospital leaders, the results of this study can be used as a benchmark for things that have and have not been implemented in implementing disaster management at Bhayangkara Hospital.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted at Bhayangkara Hospital, Banda Aceh. The concept of this research is to describe or provide an overview of the form of disaster management implementation reviewed from the theoretical framework of preparedness for emergency and/or disaster conditions in hospitals as regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number: 39 of 2014 concerning Disaster Management in Hospitals.

This type of research is descriptive qualitative which is one type of research included in the type of qualitative research. The descriptive method in this study is used to explain or describe the Commitment of Hospital Management to the Implementation of Disaster Management at Bhayangkara Hospital, Banda Aceh. The informants in this study were the Head of Binfung Sub-Division, Head of the K3RS Committee, Coordinator of the K3RS Committee for Fire and Disaster Alertness, Coordinator of the K3RS Committee for Occupational Health and Safety and Secretary of the K3RS Committee of Bhayangkara Hospital.

2.1 Types of Data and Data Sources

In this study, the types and sources of data used are:

1. Primary data is data obtained through interviews with the person in charge of the Binfung Sub-Division, Head of the K3RS Committee, Coordinator of the K3RS Committee for Fire and Disaster Alertness, Coordinator of the K3RS Committee for Occupational Health and Safety and Secretary of the K3RS Committee of Bhayangkara Hospital.
2. Secondary data is data obtained through library studies, literature, and various documents and Director's Decrees relating to hospital disaster management.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Description of Disaster Management at Bhayangkara Hospital

Bhayangkara Hospital is a general hospital owned by the Indonesian National Police domiciled in Banda Aceh City. As a level in the regulations of the Indonesian National Police Hospital, Bhayangkara Hospital is a Level IV Bhayangkara Hospital under the supervision of the Aceh Regional Police which always follows developments, both in terms of service innovation technology and new breakthroughs in health services.

Bhayangkara Hospital Banda Aceh has a Vision of "Realizing Excellent and Professional Health Services in the Health Sector for Members of the Indonesian National Police and the General Public" while the Mission is "providing excellent health services by implementing Islamic values; providing health guidance including comprehensive efforts (promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative); having professional, ethical, competitive, superior and moral human resources; becoming a standardized place of education for health workers.

In its function, the Bhayangkara Hospital of the Aceh Police, in addition to serving regular patients, also provides emergency health services during disasters, both internal and external disasters to the hospital. Disaster management activities at the Bhayangkara Hospital are carried out according to the Minister of Health Regulation No. 66 of 2016 concerning Occupational Safety and Health (K3RS) and the Minister of Health Decree No. 432/Menkes/IV/2007 concerning guidelines and management of Occupational Health and Safety in Hospitals. The procedure for implementing activities is regulated in the Decree of the Hospital Director, namely the K3RS Committee Decree. Based on the results of interviews with the Binfung Sub-Division, the Head of the K3RS Committee and 3 Committee Coordinators including the Fire and Disaster Alertness Division at the Bhayangkara Hospital.

Disaster management activities at the Bhayangkara Hospital are carried out according to the Minister of Health Regulation No. 66 of 2016 concerning Occupational Safety and Health (K3RS) and the Minister of Health Decree No. 432/Menkes/IV/2007 concerning guidelines and management of Occupational Health and Safety in Hospitals. The procedure for implementing activities is regulated in the Decree of the Hospital Director, namely the K3RS Committee Decree. Based on the results of interviews with the Binfung Sub-Division, the Head of the K3RS Committee and 3 Committee Coordinators including the Fire and Disaster Alertness Division at the Bhayangkara Hospital.

The disaster work guidelines of the Bhayangkara Hospital are in the organizational structure of the K3RS Committee, namely the Fire and Disaster Alertness Coordinator, regulated in the Decree of the Director of the Hospital. The Fire and Disaster Alertness Coordinator consists of the Head of the medical and nursing professions and members representing each work unit in the hospital listed in the organizational structure. Duties and functions are explained in the form of job descriptions and activities.

According to the Minister of Defense Regulation. 2014, the implementation of disaster management is a series of efforts that include determining disaster risk policies, prevention activities, emergency response, and rehabilitation. The implementation of disaster management in hospitals is based on disaster management documents and the implementation of disaster management can be carried out in 2 stages, namely the activation and deactivation stages. The activation stage is the process of escalating the hospital's organizational structure in normal conditions to an organizational structure in a disaster situation when a disaster occurs, and vice versa when the situation has

returned to normal, the organizational structure returns to a normal structure (deactivation) The Bhayangkara Hospital management policy for implementing disaster management is implemented based on Defense Ministerial Regulation No. 39 of 2014, but has not been fully implemented due to the absence of a disaster document (hospital disaster plan).

3.2 Description of Hospital Management's Commitment to the Implementation of Disaster Management at Bhayangkara Hospital, Banda Aceh

There are 3 things that can be assessed against the management's commitment to implementing disaster management, namely:

1. A very effective and efficient strategy by implementing the concept of activation and deactivation of the hospital's organizational structure when a disaster occurs, this application is carried out for large and widespread disasters both internal and external to the hospital so that when a disaster occurs, it can provide procedural health services.
2. Disaster policies are situational and refer to the Bhayangkara Hospital management policy rules. The implementation of disaster management is carried out based on Defense Ministerial Regulation No. 39 of 2014, but has not been fully implemented due to the absence of disaster documents (hospital disaster plan).
3. Disaster management procedures refer to the Emergency Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), the hospital has its own disaster management team that has legality through a decree authorized by the Director of the hospital. If it does not have one, the hospital is required to form a disaster management team that has been approved through a decision of the hospital leadership. The team must be able to understand disaster risk analysis, namely understanding the possibility and impact of threats that arise if a disaster occurs in the hospital, identifying potential disaster threats (hazards), assessing the impact of disaster events (consequences/severity). And understand Hospital Disaster Organization. (Sophie.ZT. 2024).

3.3 Analyzing Management Commitment to the Implementation of Disaster Management at Bhayangkara Hospital

Based on the results of observations, document reviews and interview results with all units related to this research, the commitment of the management of the Bahayangkara Hospital has existed from the beginning which was stated verbally but has not been realized in the form of a written policy specifically regarding hospital disaster planning (Hospital Disaster Plan) and disaster budget. However, regarding funding related to disaster management and facilities, it is already in the POLDA budget post, although the facilities provided are not yet complete.

Currently, disaster management in terms of hospital structure is under the Subbag Binfung and in the K3RS Committee as the Coordinator of Fire and Disaster Alertness, related to policies on disaster management can stand alone with a Director's Decree to be made and socialized together with the formation of the Hospital Disaster Management Organizational Structure. Human resources handling disasters at the Bahayangkara Hospital do not yet have special expertise in the field of disasters, existing resources need to be included in disaster training so that the hospital has competent resources that will be realized in the form of a hospital disaster management organizational forum.

4. CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Bhayangkara Hospital Disaster Management Planning System

There are several important things in disaster management planning in hospitals, including preparing a display and summary of the situation, preparing incident maps and projections, resource and situation units tasked with carrying out all check-ins, demobilization and documentation units and technical specializations, collecting and analyzing data and current information related to the incident, preparing an incident action plan. Archiving and compiling incident documents required for legal purposes, the demobilization and documentation unit is tasked with making copies of documents including the technical specialist incident action plan. When the incident is under control and has been completed, then return all resources that have been used in an organized, safe, and effective manner. To assist in incident operations, technical personnel and experts are needed to provide input and advice based on their knowledge and experience. Bhayangkara Hospital has not fully implemented and there has been no detailed preparation in the job description of the Coordinator of the K3RS Committee for Fire and Disaster Alertness regarding hospital disaster planning guidelines.

4.2 Planning Planning and Financing of Disaster Management at Bhayangkara Hospital

Hospital disaster management planning and financing consists of four main elements: hourly units, procurement units, compensation and damage units, and cost units. The hospital disaster management planning and finance department is responsible for monitoring, financing, and management related to purchases in the event of an incident.

The actual condition at Bhayangkara Hospital has implemented disaster management, although it is not perfect because disaster resources and infrastructure are still very limited. For the implementation of disaster management at Bhayangkara Hospital, management is committed to creating a Hospital Disaster Preparedness Plan Guideline Document (Hospital Disaster Plan) to improve preparedness for various types of disasters and immediately form a HDP preparation team.

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